

Effect of molding condition on mechanical properties in injection and compression hybrid molding

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid molding refers to a combination of compression molding and injection molding. Hybrid molding is a method of injecting and joining discontinuous fibers suitable for forming a complicated shape to a continuous fiber part. From now on, continuous fiber part is called intermediate material. Therefore, there is a problem in the strength of the joint part between the intermediate material and the injection resin part. In order to improve the quality of the hybrid molded product, it is important to improve the joint strength between continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic (c-FRTP) and the injection resin part. It is considered that the junction characteristic is influenced by the preheating condition of c-FRTP, the molding conditions such as the temperature, pressure. Therefore, the purpose of this research was to clarify the molding conditions and the preheating device for obtaining the optimum mechanical properties of the molded product by hybrid molding. In this research, a hybrid molding machine of a press machine and an injection machine was used. A heating test was conducted by using preheating devices, and the temperature distribution and the difference in temperature rise were investigated. In addition, the influence of the difference in the preheating condition of the intermediate material on the strength was examined by evaluation of mechanical properties, surface and cross sectional observations. From this study, middle infrared was found out to be the most suitable preheating device for hybrid molding, from its advantages that could preheat in a short time and improves mechanical property.

1 INTRODUCTION

The advantage for discontinuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite is to form a complicated shape in a short time. On the other hand, the c-FRTP has high mechanical properties, but its process ability is limited and it is difficult to produce complicated shapes such as ribs. Therefore, the hybrid molding method attracts attention. The hybrid molding method used in this research is a molding method combined the compression molding and the injection molding. Hybrid molding can take both advantage of continuous fiber and discontinuous fiber. The part of requiring strength is formed by compression molding of intermediate material with continuous fiber, and the complicated shape part is made by injection molding of discontinuous fiber. However, there is a problem with the strength of the joint part between the intermediate material part molded by compression molding and the part molded by injection molding. Joining characteristics are thought to be influenced by preheating conditions of c-FRTP, molding conditions such as temperature, pressure and speed of injection resin. Therefore, it was aimed to clarify the influence of the difference between the preheating condition for the intermediate material and the temperature of the injection resin on the mechanical properties of the molding and injection resin joint.

2 MOLDING EQUIPMENT AND TEST METHOD

2.1 Hybrid molding procedure and materials

Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of the hybrid molding machine used in this study. The hybrid molding equipment is composed of a molding die, a press machine, and an injection molding machine. The molding die used for hybrid molding is installed in the press machine, and the press machine is moved up and down to open and close the die. The molding process of the hybrid molding is shown in Figure 2. In hybrid molding, after an intermediate material such as prepreg consisting of continuous fiber and thermoplastic resin is inserted into a molding die, a preheating device is inserted into the die and heat the intermediate material. Thereafter, the preheating device is taken out, the mold is closed, pressurized, and the resin is injected. At this time, the injection resin and the intermediate material are welded by the heat from injection resin and the preheated intermediate material. After cooling, the molded product is taken out and molding is completed. In this study, different wavelengths of near infrared and middle infrared preheating devices were used as preheating devices. A completely impregnated prepreg reinforced with a glass fiber woven fabric (TEPEX dynalite 104-RG600(X), Thickness 1.5mm, Bond Laminates) was used as an intermediate material. In the injection molding material, pellets in which the resin was polypropylene and the reinforced fibers was carbon fibers was used. The weight fraction of fiber (Wf) of the pellets was 30%, and the average fiber length was 150 μm .

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of hybrid molding system.

Figure 2: Schematic drawing of molding procedure of hybrid molding.

2.2 Temperature history

In order to investigate the difference in the temperature rise characteristics of the intermediate material by each preheating devices, the temperature history was measured by attaching a

thermocouple to the heating surface irradiated with infrared rays. After 10 seconds later stop heating, temperature history of the heating surface was measured using thermography and thermal image analysis software. This temperature history was recorded to consider the time required to press the intermediate material before resin injection.

2.3 Three point bending test and cross sectional observation

The preheating condition of the intermediate material was set at seven conditions of no preliminary heating, heating temperature of 80 °C, 100 °C, 120 °C, 140, 160 °C, and 180 °C. From the result of 2.1, the heating time at which the temperature after 10 seconds from stopping the preheating of the intermediate material reached the above temperature was obtained. The injection resin temperature was two conditions of 200 °C and 240 °C. Table 1 shows the names of each specimens. The name of the specimen is shown in the order of the heating device, the preheating temperature, and the injection resin temperature. Under the condition “near infrared rays / preheating temperature 140 °C / injection resin temperature 200 °C”, take the acronym for Near infrared radiation and become N140-200. As an example, under the nonheated condition, heating method and injection resin temperature are shown in this order. The common molding conditions are shown in Table 2.

Figure. 3 shows a photograph of the molded product. The size of the molded product were 100 mm in length and 50 mm in width. The total thickness of molded product was 3 mm. Three point bending test was conducted on molding produced under various molding conditions, and the mechanical properties were evaluated. A specimen was cut out from the molded product so as to have a length of 90 mm and a width of 15 mm, and the injection resin part was set on the compression side. For the test conditions, the distance between supporting points was 60 mm and the test speed was 5 mm / min. After three point bending test, a cross section was observed in order to confirm the fracture aspect of the specimen.

Table 1: Molding conditions of each sample.

		Non heated	Near infrared radiation				
			80	100	120	140	160
Injection resin temperature	200[°C]	NH200	N80-200	N100-200	M120-200	N140-200	N160-200
	240[°C]	NH240	N80-240	N100-240	M120-240	N140-240	N160-240
		Middle infrared radiation					
		80	100	120	140	160	180
Injection resin temperature	200[°C]	M80-200	M100-200	M120-200	M140-200	M160-200	M180-200
	240[°C]	M80-240	M100-240	M120-240	M140-240	M160-240	M180-240

Table 2: Common molding conditions.

Mold temperature [°C]	95
Clamping pressure [Mpa]	20
Keeping pressure [Mpa]	23
Cooling time [sec]	40

Figure 3: Photograph of the molded product.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Temperature history

Figure 4 shows the temperature history at the surface of the intermediate material when the intermediate material was heated by each preheating devices. From figure 4 it can be confirmed that the temperature rising rate of the middle infrared ray is higher than that of the near infrared ray. In addition, the maximum temperature was higher for middle infrared heating device than for near infrared one. Figure 5 shows the relationship between the descent temperature for 10 seconds after stopping the heating and the temperature at the time of stop the heating. Even in the case the temperature just after the stop of heating is equal, the descent temperature in 10 seconds becomes larger in the middle infrared heating than in the near infrared heating. From these results, the heating time required for the surface temperature of the intermediate material at the time of molding to be 80 °C and 100 °C, 120 °C, 140 °C, 160 °C, 180 °C was obtained. Essential heating time of each molding temperatures are shown in Table 3. When heated with near infrared preheating device, the temperature could not be maintained 180°C at molding. Therefore, the condition of the preheating temperature of 180 °C by near infrared heating was excluded.

Figure 4: Relationship between surface temperature and heating time.

Figure 5: Relationship between descent temperature and heating temperature.

Table 3: Essential heating time of molding temperature.

Molding temperature[°C]	Near infrared radiation[sec]	Middle infrared radiation[sec]
80	7s	4s
100	14s	9s
120	22s	15s
140	50s	30s
160	80s	43s
180	-	53s

3.2 Three point bending test and cross sectional observation

Figure 6 shows the elastic modulus at each preheating temperature obtained from the three point bending test. Figures 6 (a) shows relationship between elastic modulus and preheating temperature under conditions of injection resin temperature at 200 °C and (b) shows conditions of injection resin temperature at 240 °C. From figure 6, the elastic modulus was around 25 GPa and there was no difference in each condition. It is considered that the preheating condition and the injection resin temperature do not affect the elastic modulus.

Figure 7 shows relationship between bending strength and preheating temperature. When the preheating temperature is from 80 °C to 120 °C, under the condition that the preheating condition and the injection resin temperature are equal, the bending strength becomes higher in the middle infrared radiation than in the near infrared radiation. The bending strength increased until the preheating temperature reached 100 °C, and when it exceeded 120 °C, the bending strength decreased. Bending strength showed the maximum value of 245 MPa under the condition of M100-240. In the same preheating condition, bending strength increased in higher injection temperature. In the non heated condition, the bending strength was about 110 MPa when the injection resin temperature was 200 °C, but when the injection resin temperature was raised to 240 °C, the bending strength became about 3 times. In Fig.8, the preheated specimen of M240-100 and M240-180 showed the largest and smallest bending strength from the load-displacement diagram. M240-180 fractured at displacement of 11 mm and the load suddenly decreased, but load reduction could not be seen clearly under other conditions.

Based on this result, cross sectional observation was carried out in order to clarify the fracture aspects. There were 4 kinds of fracture aspects. Figure 9 shows a schematic diagram of the fracture aspect that could be confirmed.

- (I) Cracks on the tensile side of the intermediate material
- (II) Cracks in the injection resin part
- (III) Delamination between intermediate material and injection resin
- (IV) Buckling of the injection resin at the compression side

Table 4 shows the fracture aspect that could be confirmed for each specimen. Cracks on the tensile side of the intermediate material part could be confirmed on all specimens. The buckling of the resin on the compression side could be confirmed only with the preheated specimen. On the other hand, when the intermediate material was not heated, buckling did not occur at the injection resin part. In addition, delamination between intermediate material and injection resin part and cracks in the injection resin part occurred in NH200 and part of NH240. It is considered that the joint strength between the intermediate material and the injection resin part was low therefore the delamination occurred before buckling. The reason why crack of resin part occurred at NH200 and NH240 is believed that the injection resin part received the load after delamination.

Figure 10 shows a cross sectional photograph of M180-240 specimen. The upper side of the red line is the injection resin part and the lower side is the intermediate material part. It can be confirmed that the left side of the figure is the destructive part and the thickness of the intermediate material part is thinner than the right side. Therefore it was examined thickness of the intermediate material to the thickness of the test piece. Table 5 shows the intermediate material thickness ratio at the destructive part and the nondestructive part of the specimen. The intermediate material thickness ratio was defined as the ratio of thickness of intermediate material to the specimen thickness. It can be confirmed that the intermediate material thickness ratio decreases as the preheating temperature and the injection resin temperature increase. It is considered that the flow ability of the intermediate material resin increased due to the increase in the molding temperature and the fibers of intermediate material flowed toward the end of the molded part at the time of injection. Figure 11 is a schematic diagram of the longitudinal direction of the specimen. Figure 11 (a) shows a specimen which the fiber is not undulated, and figure 11 (b) shows a specimen which the fiber is undulated. A wavy line shows a 0° fiber bundle, an oval shows a 90° fiber bundle, and a black circle shows a reinforced fiber. In both (a) and (b), the final destruction occurred near the center of the specimen. In (b), cracks were confirmed inside the 90° fiber bundle. From these results, a difference was clearly confirmed in the destruction form. In order to clarify the destruction mechanism of (b), an intermediate stopping bending test of M240-180 was conducted. The crack occurred in the resin part and inside the 90° fiber bundle of which volume fraction of fiber between 0° fiber bundle decreased. Thereafter, the crack increased its amount and propagated. And fractured near the center of specimen. The point where the volume fraction of fiber decreased because the undulation of the fiber increased as the molding temperature increased, and the distance between the layers increased. When the preheating temperature exceeds 120°C , the undulation of the fiber became large and the crack increases at the part where the volume fraction of fiber decreases. It was considered that the bending strength decreased from these result.

(a) Injection resin temperature 200°C

(b) Injection resin temperature 200°C

Figure 6: Relationship between elastic modulus and preheating temperature.

Figure 7: Relationship between bending strength and preheating temperature.

Figure 8: Relationship between load and displacement.

Figure 9: Schematic drawing of destruction.

Table 4: fracture aspect of various specimens.

Sample name	I	II	III	IV
NH200	○	○	○	
NH240	○	○	○	
N140-200	○			○
N160-200	○			○
N140-240	○			○
N160-240	○			○
M140-200	○			○
M160-200	○			○
M180-200	○			○
M140-240	○			○
M160-240	○			○
M180-240	○			○

Figure 10: Cross sectional photograph of M180-240 .

Table 5: Intermediate material thickness ratio of each specimen.

Sample name	Substrate thickness ratio[%]	
	Non destructive part	Destructive part
M140-200	46	49
M160-200	50	45
M180-200	50	46
M140-240	47	46
M160-240	53	40
M180-240	55	24
N140-200	47	43
N160-200	47	41
N140-240	46	43
N160-240	50	38
NH200	46	47
NH240	50	50

Figure 11: Schematic diagram of fiber undulation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this research, it was aimed to clarify the influence of the preheating condition of the intermediate material and the injection resin temperature condition on the mechanical properties of the molded product. The temperature rising rate of the middle infrared ray is higher than that of the near infrared ray. In addition, the maximum temperature was higher for middle infrared heating than for near infrared. The temperature just after the stop of heating is equal, the descent temperature in 10 seconds becomes larger in the middle infrared heating than in the near infrared heating. It is considered that the injection resin temperature and the preheating condition do not affect the elastic modulus. The bending strength increased until the preheating temperature reached 100 °C, and when it exceeded 120 °C, the bending strength decreased. It is considered that the flowability of the intermediate material resin increased due to the increase in the molding temperature and the fibers flowed toward the end of the molded part at the time of injection. The higher the molding temperature, the greater the disorder of the fiber, the more the distance between the layers and the lower the volume fraction of fiber. From these facts, it is considered that the bending strength decreased when the preheating temperature exceeded 120 °C. From this study, middle infrared was found out to be the most suitable preheating device for hybrid molding, from its advantages that could preheat in a short time and improves mechanical property.